

ISic3294

I.Sicily inscription 3294

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 241

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κίτε Ο

2. ὑρανία Ούρανί

3. ου Θυγάτηρ ζή

4. σασα ἔτη ἔπ τά Θανοῦσα

6. Φεβραρείω μ[η]

7. ν[]ὶ πέντε [] []

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Here lies Ourania, daughter of Ouranios. She lived for seven years, having died five [days into] in the month Februrary...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645561

PHI 316281

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 201

Libertini, G 1930. Il Museo Biscari. Milan. At 316 no.1

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